

FATIGUE-INDUCED DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES INFLUENCED BY MEAN STRESS AND FIBRE VOLUME CONTENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper selected results of a study investigating the combined effect of fibre volume content, anisotropy, load amplitude and mechanical mean stress on the mechanical behaviour and the fatigue damage mechanisms of unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates are presented. Laminates with 30 % and 55 % fibre volume fraction were tested at angles of 0°, 45° and 90° under tensile and compressive loads in quasi-static and fatigue tests. Results show that the fibre volume content increases the mechanical properties in tension-tension fatigue tests for all tested angles. The tensile damage mechanisms in off-axis specimens change from matrix cracking and matrix-fibre debonding to fibre-pull out with an increasing amount of fibres. Tension-compression tests showed that higher fibre volume contents are only beneficial in fatigue tests at angles of 0° and 45°. Fatigue strengths of UD 90° specimens in tension-compression tests are not significantly improved by the fibre volume content.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics offer extraordinary potentials for the application in lightweight structures. However, in the applications in which composite materials are most superior e.g. in vehicles or aircrafts the occurrence of cyclic loads is very likely. Mechanical loads or temperature changes over time are known to induce fatigue, which is furthermore connected with the decrease of mechanical properties such as stiffness or strength.

To be able to understand the fatigue processes in composites or to possibly build predictive theories on physical damage mechanisms in the future, the characterisation of the degradation within in the material is of tremendous importance. Reifsnider e.g. [1–3], Talreja e.g. [4–6], Stinchcomb e.g. [7,8] and others performed fundamental studies describing the damage modes which composites pass through during their fatigue life. The basic mechanisms investigated in these studies of matrix-cracks which grow, interact and lead to single fibre failures or bigger damages such as delamination finally resulting in the separation of the composite are well-accepted up to now. However, it is also known that each material possesses its unique damage mechanisms and that influences such as anisotropy or stacking sequence significantly influence the initiation and progress of damage.

To address a few of the effects on fatigue-induced damage mechanisms, carbon/epoxy laminates with two different fibre volume fractions were produced in this work. The effect of different fibre volume contents on the fatigue damage behaviour might be of special interest because the amount of fibres may vary within components due to the production process. Consequently, if areas with different fibre contents exist within components the performance in the application might be affected. Furthermore, knowing the mechanical properties in dependency of the fibre volume content may allow the creation of fatigue material laws shortening the experimental test time. Unidirectional laminates were tested at angles of 0°, 45° and 90° in relation to the fibre direction in fatigue tests with different mechanical

mean stresses. Fracture surfaces were investigated comprehensively with scanning electron microscopy. The fatigue load cases, whether tension-tension or tension-compression loads were applied, resulted in different damage mechanisms in combination with the influence of the fibre content. Fatigue tests were evaluated in terms of stress-strain hysteresis loops and also S-N curves. By correlating the experimental results with the investigated damage mechanisms the understanding for the unique damage behaviour of the investigated material and the significant influence of fibre volume fraction could be deepened.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Carbon/epoxy specimens with aspired 30 % and 55 % fibre volume fraction and also epoxy resin plates were produced. The fibre volume fractions were verified with thermogravimetric analysis. During these tests, the samples were heated under nitrogen atmosphere (N₂) up to 700 °C with 5 K/min and cooled down to 200 °C. Subsequently, the procedure switched from nitrogen to oxygen atmosphere (O₂) and samples were heated up to 800 °C [9]. Unidirectional (UD) carbon/epoxy specimens were milled from plates with diamond blades at angles of 0°, 45° and 90°. Specimen geometries were 200x20x2 mm for UD 45° and UD 90° specimens. For UD 0° specimens, a geometry of 200x10x1 mm was used for specimens with high fibre volume fraction and 200x10x2 mm for specimens with low fibre volume fraction. Free gauge lengths were 100 mm for tensile and 10 mm for compressive loads.

Mechanical tests were performed on a servo-hydraulic test machine MTS 810 designed for loads up to 100 kN by MTS Systems Corporations (Minnesota, USA) equipped with a 100 kN load cell at room temperature. Tension-tension fatigue tests were performed with the *R*-value (= minimum force / maximum force) of 0.1, tension-compression fatigue tests with *R* = -1 until fracture. Maximum cyclic stresses between approximately 80 % and 65 % of the ultimate tensile strengths were chosen as load levels for UD 0° and between 60 % and 35 % for the tested off-axis specimens in tension-tension fatigue tests. In tension-compression fatigue tests, the maximum cyclic tensile stresses applied were between approximately 25 % and 15 % of the ultimate tensile strengths for UD 0° specimens and between approximately 65 % and 25 % for off-axis specimens [10]. Ultimate tensile strength and ultimate compressive strengths were determined according to the standards [11] and [12], respectively, in preliminary tests [9,10]. Specimens were usually tested at four different stress levels with a minimum of three specimens being tested on each stress level. If number of cycles exceeded 2*10⁶, tests were usually stopped. Force-displacement hysteresis loops were recorded in all fatigue tests by the test machine. Due to the small free gauge length of only 10 mm for tension-compression fatigue tests making local displacement measurement difficult, the displacements used for strain calculation of the representative stress-strain hysteresis discussed in this paper were recorded by the test machine's piston. Fracture surfaces of failed specimens were investigated in detail by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with 200x and 1000x magnification.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In figure 1, results of thermogravimetric analysis are presented in terms of mean normalised weight vs time. The applied test procedure is illustrated with dashed lines. Epoxy resin specimens and carbon/epoxy specimens with both fibre contents showed a first mass decrease between 350 °C and 450 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. This temperature range is typical for the pyrolysis of polymeric materials under inert atmosphere [13]. After cooling down of the samples to 200 °C, the atmosphere was switched from nitrogen to oxygen. During heating-up under oxygen atmosphere, a small mass decrease was detected at around 450 °C, which was too low to be a possible temperature range for the pyrolysis of carbon fibres [13]. Because the mass decrease was smaller for specimens with high fibre content it seemed that this effect was caused by the matrix material in the specimens. Therefore, TGA measurements with pure epoxy resin using the same test procedure as for carbon/epoxy plates were done as well. The mass decrease of epoxy resin at around 450 °C could be attributed to oxidation of pyrolysis carbon black which had been formed previously by the resin under N₂ atmosphere. The carbon fibres in carbon/epoxy specimens finally combusted under O₂ atmosphere between 550 °C and 700 °C. Density measurements provided mean density of 1.5 g/m³ for composites with high fibre

content and 1.3 g/m³ for low fibre content [9]. By using the average fibre weight contents of 0.63 for high and 0.39 for low fibre content measured with TGA for calculation, the aspired fibre volume contents of 55 % and 30 % could be confirmed [9].

Figure 1: Results of thermogravimetric analysis of carbon/epoxy plates with high and low fibre content and pure epoxy resin from [9].

As an example for the combined influence of fibre volume fraction and mechanical mean stress under fatigue loads, fracture surfaces of UD 90° specimens with 30 % and 55 % fibre volume and UD 0° specimens are discussed in the following. The respective stress-strain hysteresis loops recorded in tension-tension and tension-compression fatigue tests are also presented. The investigated fracture surfaces of UD 45° specimens and all measured S-N curves are not included herein but are published in [9,10]. Fracture surfaces of UD 90° specimens with 30 % fibre fraction tested in tension-tension fatigue tests are illustrated in figure 2a and 2b while figure 2c and 2d present fracture surfaces of a specimen tested in a tension-compression fatigue test. On the contrary, fracture surfaces of UD 90° with 55 % fibre volume content are illustrated in figure 3. Again, fractures surfaces after tension-tension fatigue tests are presented at the left hand side and fracture surfaces after tension-compression tests on the right.

Specimens with low fibre volume content (figure 2a and 2b) showed a clearly different damage behaviour compared to the specimen with high fibre content (figure 3a and 3b) after being tested in tension-tension fatigue tests as presented in [9,10]. While in specimens with low fibre volume content matrix cracking and interfacial debonding were the dominant failure mechanisms, fibre pull-out was monitored on fracture surfaces of specimens with high fibre content. Beyond that it was observed that damage mechanisms depended on the applied load amplitude. At high load amplitudes the damage behaviour was more similar than at lower load amplitudes where more pulled out fibres were found on specimens with high fibre content [9]. The fibre volume content affected the fracture surfaces in tension-compression fatigue tests as well, as figure 3c and especially figure 3d emphasize [10]. UD 90° specimens with low fibre content showed almost even fracture surfaces without a significant amount of fibres being pulled out from the fractures surface [9]. On the contrary, in UD 90° specimens with high fibre content a broken fibre bundle and fragments of broken fibres lying on the fracture

surface are visible (figure 3c, 200x magnification). Figure 3d (1000x magnification) presents the fractured fibres in greater detail. The broken fibres were still embedded in the matrix material which was usually not the case with the pulled-out fibres observed in tension-tension tests (figure 3b). Besides, the matrix material appeared more damaged in tension-compression tests [10].

Figure 2: Fracture surfaces of UD 90° 30 % specimens tested at $R = 0.1$ ($\sigma_a = 5.64$ MPa, $N_f = 1.2 \cdot 10^5$) with 200x (a) and 1000x (b) magnification and at $R = -1$ ($\sigma_a = 6$ MPa, $N_f = 1.5 \cdot 10^5$) with 200x (c) and 1000x (d) magnification from [9,10]

Figure 3: Fracture surfaces of UD 90° 55 % specimens tested at $R = 0.1$ ($\sigma_a = 6.75$ MPa, $N_f = 1.9 \cdot 10^5$) with 200x (a) and 1000x (b) magnification and at $R = -1$ ($\sigma_a = 7.5$ MPa, $N_f = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$) with 200x (c) and 1000x (d) magnification from [9,10].

The respective stress-strain hysteresis loops for UD 90° specimens with high fibre content for stress ratios $R = 0.1$ and $R = -1$ are illustrated in figure 4. The shapes of the hystereses correlated with the monitored damage mechanisms. In fatigue tests with $R = 0.1$, the last hysteresis slope measured immediately before failure was shifted to significantly higher strains (figure 4a). The stress-strain hysteresis loops indicated that failure happened suddenly during the last 1000 cycles of the fatigue test. The fibre pull-out observed in SEM investigations might be responsible for the shift to higher strains. However, the shape of the hystereses did not change during the fatigue test. In contrast to that, stress-strain hystereses measured in tension-compression fatigue test indicated a different material behaviour. The last two illustrated hystereses measured after $2 \cdot 10^5$ and $2.1 \cdot 10^5$ in combination with the damage mechanisms presented in figure 3c and 3d suggested the following damage mechanisms: while tension loads pulled the fibres a little bit out of the fracture plane as monitored in fatigue test with $R = 0.1$, the consequential compression load seemed to press the fibres either in the more and more damaged matrix material or against other fibres. In this case, in specimens with high fibre content it would be more likely that fibres were pressed against each other which might even result in local bending load and consequently in broken fibre bundles (figure 3d) [10]. If a specimen, which was already damaged by the compressive load part, was loaded with tension subsequently the already broken fibres could not be pulled out anymore resulting in the stress-strain behaviour illustrated in the last hystereses in figure 4 where the tensile load was finally critical for failure of the specimen [10].

Figure 4: Representative stress-strain hystereses of UD 90° 55 % tested with $R = 0.1$ (left) and $R = -1$ (right) from [10].

The fracture surfaces of UD 0° with both fibre volume contents were too uneven to be investigated by scanning electron microscopy. Therefore, representative photographs of UD 0° with high fibre volume content are illustrated in figure 5 [10]. Fracture surfaces of UD 0° with low fibre volume content showed features comparable to specimens with high fibre content. After tension-tension fatigue tests pulled out fibres and broken single fibres or fibres bundles were usually observed (figure 5a). In UD 0° specimens tested in tension-compression fatigue tests, fibre breakage either in a few fracture planes as shown in figure 5b or fibre breakage along only one fracture plane were dominant damage mechanisms. The corresponding stress-strain hystereses are presented in figure 6. In tension-tension fatigue tests, the stress-strain hystereses were shifted to higher strains during the first $2.5 \cdot 10^5$ cycles of the fatigue test. Only for the last hysteresis measured after $2.92 \cdot 10^5$ cycles immediately before failure the slope changed as well. In tension-compression fatigue tests on the contrary, the stress-strain hysteresis overturned during the tests. That would indicate that the tensile and compression stiffnesses of the specimen decreased. This observation might be argued by continuously developing fibre breakage in the specimens due to compressive loads weakening the tensile and

compressive behaviour of UD 0° specimens finally resulting fracture surfaces as illustrated in figure 5b [10].

Figure 5: UD 0° specimens with 55 % fibre volume content tested with stress ratios (a) $R = 0.1$ and (b) $R = -1$ from [10].

Figure 6: Representative stress-strain hystereses of UD 0° 55 % tested with $R = 0.1$ (left) and $R = -1$ (right) from [10].

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The comprehensive results of UD 0°, UD 45° and UD 90° with low and high fibre content published in [9,10] are schematically summarised in figure 7. The quasi-static, fatigue and damage behaviour is illustrated in a comparative way. Results showed that in quasi-static tensile and compressive tests, a higher amount of fibres resulted always in higher tensile and compressive strengths, respectively. For UD 0° specimens, quasi-static compressive strength was about 30 % of the tensile strength. On the contrary, UD 45° and UD 90° possessed twice or three times higher compressive than tensile strengths [9,10]. As a consequence of the quasi-static behaviour, nominal stress amplitude σ_a in tension-tension fatigue tests was always higher for specimens with high fibre volume content. In fatigue tests at $R = 0.1$, UD 0° and UD 45° specimens with high fibre volume content were tested at higher nominal stress amplitudes than their counterparts with low fibre content. In UD 90° specimens, the fibre volume content mainly influenced fatigue tests in the high cycle fatigue regime due to damage mechanisms changing from fibre pull-out at high stress levels to matrix cracking at lower levels in specimens with 30 % fibre volume content [9]. In tension-compression fatigue tests, nominal stress amplitudes σ_a for UD 0° were lower and amplitudes for off-axis specimens were higher or similar compared to tension-tension fatigue tests. For UD 90° specimens, the fibre volume content did not influence the fatigue strength in tension-compression fatigue tests significantly. Damage mechanisms in UD 0° changed from pull out and fracture of single fibres at $R = 0.1$ to breakage of fibre bundles at $R = -1$. In off-axis specimens, matrix cracking and fibre pull-out were dominant damage mechanisms in tests with $R = 0.1$. In contrast to that breakage of fibre bundles and fragments of crushed fibres were observed on the fracture surfaces after tension-compression fatigue tests [10]. Crushed fibre bundles were mainly found in specimens with high fibre content which might explain the observation that an increased fibre volume content was not beneficial in tension-compression tests transverse to fibre direction [10]. Based on the found results, the attempt will be made to create material laws taking the combined influence of fibre volume fraction and

anisotropy into account. Adequate material laws may be beneficial as support for life-time prediction tools for composite parts.

Figure 7: Schematic summary of investigated mechanical behaviour and damage mechanisms in unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates depending on the fibre volume content, the test angle, the applied load type and fatigue mean stress, respectively [10].

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